

Use case fact-sheet

Actors

List all actors involved in the Use Case and the Geographic Information-related processes they are involved in, then put a “x” in correspondence to the relevant cells.

Who (actor) ²	What (Action) ¹					
	Data acquisition/creation	Data analysis/processing/validation	Data publication	Extraction of information from published data	Data maintenance	xxx
Municipality	x		x		x	
Decision makers				x		
Officers/technicians		x				
Researchers	x					
General Public				x		
xxx						

Table 1: Overview of the actors involved in the Use Case

Use Case (UC) main info	
Identifier	LEU_BD_01
Name	Identification of potential Extensive Green Roofs(EGRs) locations
Description	This use case will identify the suitable locations for installing green roofs within the municipality of Leuven by investigating their geographic potential
Primary User	Decision-makers, municipality, General public
Goal	To provide various stakeholders with information that will contribute to greening initiatives in the city.
Owner	KU Leuven
Status	under development
Policy context	
Challenges & Priorities	Leuven is vulnerable to climate change and there is a need to take action against its impact to ensure the quality of life in the city. The main risks are:

¹ Add new processes or rename the existing ones or split the ones currently merged as you may find more appropriate

² Add new actors or rename the existing ones

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drought and depletion of water resources: diagnosis developed in drought study; - Heat stress in heavily hardened neighbourhoods where risk groups live; - Water nuisance and erosion from rainwater run-off: potential nuisance and measures discussed in haemelwater(rainwater) plan and erosion control plan; - Loss of ecosystem space and biodiversity
Strategy/Plan/Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The multi-year plan 2020 - 2025 of the city of Leuven: The multi-year policy plan 2020-2025 of the city describes the city's objectives and plans during the current legislative term: https://leuven.be/sites/leuven.be/files/documents/2019-10/baanbrekend_leuven - bestuursnota 2019-2025.pdf <p>In the multi-year plan, the city of Leuven expresses its overall ambition to become a careful, green and prosperous city. The multi-year plan is structured around ten specific ambitions which are translated into programmes. Among these ten programmes, which are further detailed into action programmes, there is a programme on a 'Sustainable, climate resilient and circular city', which relates with "the challenge of moving towards a sustainable, climate-neutral society, while keeping in mind the social aspect".</p> <p>In terms of action programmes, there's an action programme on "Safeguarding open space and strengthening space for water and green" and an action programme on a "Green and resilient city". Greening measures (including green roofs) are mentioned under both programmes, stating that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The city wants to encourage residents to create green roofs, green façades and greenhouses. While the city itself will carry out a number of exemplary projects, projects on green roofs and green facades will be integrated in neighbourhood (development) initiatives. Moreover, the city will look into the possibility of further subsidising or providing practical support for the construction of green façades and roofs. - Green areas in the city are essential in reducing so-called heat islands during the summer months. Green roofs and green facades are among the measures considered to help reduce heat islands. - The city will work on water quantity control through various measures, including, water management, infiltration measures, rainwater installations, wadis, buffer basins, softening measures and also green roofs. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (2019) Leuven 2030 Roadmap 2025 · 2035 · 2050: A co-created roadmap to climate neutrality by 2050, formally endorsed by 15 key stakeholders and outlining actions across ten thematic and three cross-cutting programs: Roadmap_Leuven2030.pdf

	<p>The Roadmap consists of thirteen programs on themes such as energy, mobility and climate adaptation, each containing several specific climate actions, which citizens, organisations and governments can take to contribute to help the city towards climate neutrality. One of these programs is focused on the “Green and resilient city”, stating that “regardless of whether or not Leuven achieves the goal of climate neutrality by 2050, additional measures will be required to cope with the effects of climate change. Such adaptive measures have the added benefit of enhancing the city’s quality of life”.</p> <p>Among the measures proposed are the expansion of green spaces in the city, by planting more trees and by creating new green spaces in and outside the city, on public but also private land. More specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Paved spaces (squares, parking lots, playgrounds,...) will be greened and unsealed. - Buildings will be outfitted with green roofs and green facades. - Biodiversity in the built environment will be enhanced. <p>In terms of greening measures on private land, the city is targeting (private) owners of larger green areas (e.g. the university), larger construction projects, but also individual citizens. It is argued that the different measures will help mitigate the heat-island effect and will strengthen the city’s resilience to heavy rainfall and droughts. At the same time, these measures will have a positive impact on air quality and on public health.</p>
<p>Local Green Deal / City contract(s)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● (2021) Climate Action Plan 2020-2025: A plan aligned to the Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan that defines actions across 10 domains, identifies action owners, and establishes time frames for implementation: https://www.leuven.be/klimaatactieplan <p>In its climate action plan the city confirms its commitment to become climate neutral and climate resilient by 2050. While the Climate Action Plan strongly deals with climate mitigation, there’s also a section on climate adaptation, which contains priorities, measures and actions in three different areas: greening, water management and heat control.</p> <p>With regard to greening, the city wants to maximise its green areas and develop a network of green areas together with the system of waterways and streams (the so-called blue-green network). Also the greening of streets, squares and buildings will be promoted and supported. There are also dedicated measures dealing with the greening of semi-public and private domains and buildings. Most of these measures are about promoting and supporting ‘green’ or ‘nature-based’ solutions. Promotion will be done via dedicated campaigns and also through the realisation of some exemplary projects in the public domain. Support could consist of providing practical advice and support (e.g. on constructing green roofs or</p>

	<p>facades), over subsidies to wider community engagement projects. Measures could also focus on future construction or development projects, requiring them to execute a biodiversity assessment or meet particular green standards.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (2023) Climate City Contract: Being one of the 100 cities selected by the European Commission for the mission '100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030', the city together with Leuven 2030 developed the first Leuven climate contract, which contains different innovative breakthrough projects and associated commitments from partners from the entire Leuven society: https://netzerocities.app/resource-4188 <p>The action plan - which is part of the Climate City Contract - focuses on five major – emission - domains: renewable energy, buildings, transport and mobility, green infrastructure and circular economy and waste. Greening measures – in the public and private domain – are covered under the domain of green infrastructure. A key dimension is the greening of the built environment, which is achieved through interventions such as the removal of impermeable surfaces, the planting of trees, and the introduction of green walls and green roofs.</p>
European Green Deal Policy Area	<p>-Adaptation to climate change.</p> <p>-Nature-based solutions and green infrastructure (e.g. tree-planting, nature regeneration and greening of urban areas.)</p> <p>-Biodiversity and protected areas.</p>
Precondition	
<p><i>List the pre-requisites (availability of input data, tools, etc.)</i></p> <p>Necessary input data are available: Surface materials, DSM, Building stock</p> <p>Tools are either available: DesktopGIS, Roof Slope delineation tool</p>	
Postcondition	
DRI (Decision Ready Information)	<p>Potential Extensive Green Roof locations</p> <p>https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/b73111f6-847a-4d4c-953e-892708daa93e</p>
Use of DRI	<p>Identify and potentially incentivize building owners to install green roofs, as well as monitor and prioritise premiums disbursements.</p>
Use case processing steps	
<p>UC BPMN LEU BD1 green_roofs.drawio - draw.io (diagrams.net)</p>	
DOI to processing steps BPMN	
<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15118270</p>	
Additional remarks	

